
A Critical Study of Self-Management Lessons From Karma Yoga of Bhagavad Gita In The Today's Life

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Abstract:

In 21st century self management is crucial factor to prove and develop oneself. Even students of the college are in stress, due to cut throat competition in market. It is very difficult for every student to manage as expectations from parents, industry and society are increases day by day. As a result everyone expect to get merit number, prizes. Target oriented study mainly focuses on marks and merits. Acquiring of knowledge is basic object of education system. But due to changing situation in liberalization, privatization and globalization.

Even in this situation, if students will be able to handle different situations by using self management as included in Karma yoga of Bhagavad Gita. Meditation, mindfulness, self control are different ways for self management. Ultimate satisfaction and happiness will be achieved though self management when work and study without expecting results will be practiced. For this purpose study of self management lessons from karma yoga of Bhagavad Gita is very much needed.

Introduction:

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Objectives of the Study:

1. To Study awareness of karma yoga in Bhagavad Gita in college students.
2. To Study the practices of self management in college students.
3. To Suggest Remedies

Limitation of the study-

This study is limited only to students of D. P. Bhosale College, Koregaon Dist. Satara

Review of Literature:

Kanfer, Frederick H. Gaelick-Buys, Lisa (1991) published research paper titled as Self-management methods. The study reveals general structure for behavioral interview therapy a theoretical framework of self-regulation. It includes methods for therapeutic change tasks and assignments, creating the context

for change, contracts, modification of the environment, self-monitoring, changing self-generated behavioral consequences, self-generated aversive consequences.

Kate R. Lorig, Dr.P.H., Halsted R. Holman, M.D. (2003) published research paper titled as Self-management education: History, definition, outcomes, and mechanisms. Study includes three tasks—medical, role and emotional management. It also includes six skills like resource utilization, the formation of a patient-provider partnership, action planning, problem solving, decision making, and self-tailoring. This article covers history of self-management. Papers also includes evidence of the effectiveness of self-management interventions and posits a possible mechanism. In conclusion the article discusses problems and solutions for integrating self-management education into the mainstream health care systems.

Dharmrajsinh Pravinsinh Chauhan (2005) published paper on Mythical Concept of Karmayogaincluded in the book ‘The Foreigner’ by Arun Joshi. The book was published in 1968. Book focuses on debate on the Indian English literary terrain. Joshi attempts to demonstrate that people are using the mythical concept of Karmayoga which is included in the second and third chapters of the Gita, in the construction of the foreigner's primary subject, which is devotion to life and practice rather than passive detachment. In reality, he distinguishes between detachment and attachment. Joshi is influenced by the *Bhagawad Gita* in the formulation Bhagvad Gita unjustifiably interpreted as an illustration of Lord Krishna's Karmik. The present paper examines how the Hindu philosophy associated with the *Bhagavad Gita* aids the characters in overcoming life's challenges. An effort has been made to investigate the theistic and atheistic perspectives of characters, as well as how beliefs aid in their survival.

Simon Pearse Brodbeck (2007) published research paper entitled as Cricket and the Karmayoga A comparative study of peak performance. This paper focuses the idea of ‘non-attached action’, a non-teleological attitude allied to peak performance within armies and sports teams.. This attitude is related specifically to cricket through analysis of typical accounts (of the kind given by ex-player commentators) of the psychological approach of expert cricketers, and through comparison with the philosophy taught by Krishna to Arjuna in the *Bhagavadgita*. Particular attention is paid to notions of non-agentive behaviour, of playing one's ‘natural game’ and of being ‘in the zone’, and to techniques of mental preparation and mental hygiene. The essay is framed by a wider juxtaposition of cricketing activity and discourse with martial activity and discourse in the *Mahabharata* and in Europe.

Gobinda Bhattacharjee (2021) published Research Paper titled as A Study on Karmayoga in Bhagavad Gita. The philosophy of ‘karma’ is a doctrine to consider being the foundation stone of the entire Indian Philosophical outlook. The *Bhagavad Gita* is most beloved scripture of Indian thought and one of the prime chapters of this scripture is the ‘law of karma’. According to it, every man profit from what he does and suffers from what he does. Karmayogais mainly based on *niskam-karma*. We have to give up the attachment and the fruit regarding the action. So, the action is our *Svadharm*a, fruit or result is not our concern. The *Gita* said that the nature of *Karma* was natural, inherent in man’s existence and everybody has to work. Hence an attempt is made here to discuss the law of *karma* as considered by the *Bhagavad Gita*.

Michael J. Mahoney (2023) published research paper on research issues in self management. He discussed different issues on self management like covert behavior modification, the viability to self-

management, the relative efficacy of various self-management techniques, the necessary conditions for maintenance of self-managing, the current status of self-imposed consequences and the role of stimulus variable.

Research Methodology:

This study is based on primary data which is collected through Google forms questionnaire. Total student respondents from D. P. Bhosale College, Koregaon. Secondary data is collected through books, Magazines, Research Articles, News papers, Blogs, websites.

Concept of Self management:

Self-management are the abilities that allow everyone to control your thoughts, emotions, and behaviors to effectively achieve your goals. They empower you to take charge of your life and direct it purposefully. Self-management involves self-awareness, self-control, self-motivation, and the ability to adopt new behaviors or change old unproductive habits. Self management is buzz word in today's era. As expectations from different stakeholders are increasing day by day. Even completion in education field turns the students to examination based approach.

Self management skills include Time management, goal setting, self discipline, stress management, problem solving, adaptability, self reflection and many more. Even developing strong self management provides us foundation for personal effectiveness and success in life. It is based on your life objectives and values preserved. Self management is useful for pursuing goals in a purposeful and focused manner. Self management skills are essential for the purpose of achieving goals, empowering personal growth, handling different responsibilities, managing emotions, achieving consistency, enabling work success.

Concept of Karmyoga in Bhagvad Gita:

Karm Yoga is self less action which is covered as philosophy of work and action derived from the Bhagvad Gita. It is one of the most important spiritual novel. It advocates performing everyone's duties and responsibilities without attachment of results or outcomes. It means that without worrying about success, failure, rewards, or recognition doing of work to best of your ability is needed. The idea behind it is that focusing on the process rather than outcome. Individuals can reduce anxiety, pressure and stress through self less action. It will lead to more peaceful and fulfilling work experience. Karm Yoga promotes a sense of inner calm and detachment. It allows to handle work related challenges.

Karm Yoga is rightly applicable to students of the college. It will be helpful to develop holistically. Success does not mean in money only but it must be on the basis of happiness and satisfaction. For self management meditation and mindfulness programme is very much required.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

On the basis of this the study has been organized regarding self management and karm Yoga relevance awareness in college students of D.P. Bhosale College, Koregaon District Satara. For that purpose google form questionnaire has been prepared. And primary data is collected. Data analysis and interpretation shows as follows-

1. In present era, Whether you have to face Stress / work pressure / Study pressure while in work / on duty?

On this question, out of 145 respondents 62.76% (91 respondents) has responded stress at sometimes. 15.86% (23 respondents) responded as often and always. It is inferred that that stress or study pressure is on students. As semester examinations are conducted by University. As a result, mental stress is on students.

2. To what extent do you apply the principles of Karma Yoga (performing duties without attachment to outcomes) in your daily work?

For this question, 22.07% (32 respondents) responded answer as Always, while 32.41% (47 respondents) responded Often. Even 33.10% (48 respondents) as sometimes. It is inferred that application of principles of Karma Yoga, students are using in their life. This application is useful to normalize stress in life.

3. How often do you engage in practices that align with Karma Yoga, such as mindfulness, meditation?

On this question, 25.52% (37 respondents) responded daily using, while 15.86% (23 respondents) practicing it in every week. It is revealed that students are engaging practices daily or weekly which are align with Karma Yoga. For stress management it is important.

4. In present days, What is your opinion regarding Meditation or Mindfulness for self management ?

On this question 69.66% (101 respondents) responded meditation is most required. While 17.93% (26 respondents) responded as meditation is required at sometimes. It is inferred that most of respondents felt necessary meditation to overcome the problem of stress.

5. Are you interested to learn /read more about Karma yoga for Self Management?

On this question, 58.62% (85 respondents) responded as more interest to learn karma yoga for self management. While 32.41% (47 respondents) responded as upto some extent they are ready to learn Karma Yoga for self management. It is inferred that most of respondents are ready to learn Karma Yoga for self management.

6. In upcoming period, are you ready to spend time for meditation/mindfulness for Self Management?

On this question (51.72%) 75 respondents are ready to spare daily time for meditation and 24.83% (36 respondents) ready to spare time once in a week. It is inferred that due to increased stress level, students are ready to spare time. Even students are engaged in academic, sports, cultural and many other activities in college life. Even they are ready to spare time. It shows importance of meditation. It is revealed that meditation is very much required for college students.

Findings:

From the above analysis and interpretation, it is found that students are facing stress problem. It is found that self management is required to overcome stress in students. It is also found that students are ready to learn Karma Yoga and ready to spare time for meditation and mindfulness.

Suggestions:

On the basis of this study it is suggested that college to arrange short term course on meditation. As this course will be useful for every student in self management.

Conclusion:

Stress is vital part of everyone's life. Even students have to face study pressure due to competition. For this purpose self management as described in Karma Yoga is much needed. Meditation or mindfulness programs will be beneficial to students to overcome this situation. Even students are ready to spare time for that purpose which clearly shows necessity of meditation course. Mental fitness is very much required for every student to achieve success and happiness in life.